

Strengthening Mechanism of Silicon Carbide Green Body via Cellulose Nanofiber Addition

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1. Introduction

Robocasting for ceramics

Ceramic slurry

- Shear thinning
 - Yield stress
- Robocasting requires the slurry which shows Bingham-pseudoplastic behavior.

Ceramic green body

- Low strength
 - Brittleness
- The green body can easily collapse by shocks. (ex. Transportation from a modeling stage to a furnace)

ABSTRACT

This study has reported the enhancement of a SiC green body by CNF slurry addition to the SiC slurry for robocasting. Three-point flexural strength of the green body containing CNF was about 1.5 times higher than that without CNF. The enhancement was caused by an increase in the number of hydrogen-bonding site. On the other hand, the strengthening mechanism changed to an increase in the number of non-polar groups site after annealing.

Reinforcement

Cellulose nanofiber (CNF) aqueous slurry

- shows **Bingham-pseudoplastic behavior**.
- forms **rigid CNF sheet** after drying at room temperature through hydrogen-bonding.
- Desorption of bound water begins at 250 °C, and pyrolysis occurs at more than 300 °C drastically.

Objectives

- Enhancement of the green body by the CNF addition.
- Proposing a mechanism of the enhancement by the CNF addition.

2. Methods, Results and Discussion

Raw materials

- Silicon Carbide (SiC) powder (solid loading of 40 vol%)
- Boron carbide and Carbon powders (sintering additives)
- Water and 2 wt.% commercial CNF aqueous slurry (dispersion medium)
- Anionic dispersant

Specimens

- Different weight ratio (water-to-CNF slurry) in the dispersion media (100:0 and 80:20)
- Room temperature (RT) drying for a day.
- Annealing at 250 °C or 500 °C to investigate the strengthening mechanism.

Evaluation

- Three-point flexural test. (crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min, support span of 30 mm)
- Three-point flexural test after heat treatment.
- Microstructural observation of the green bodies and CNF.

Flexural strength of green bodies

Flexural strength σ_T^i

Composition of CNF $i = 0$ or 0.2
Annealing temperature $T = RT, 250$ or 500

$$\sigma_{RT}^{0.2} > \sigma_{RT}^0$$

CNF strengthened the SiC green body.

$$\sigma_{RT}^{0.2} > \sigma_{250}^{0.2} \approx \sigma_{RT}^0$$

CNF did not work as reinforcement after annealing at 250 °C.

$$\sigma_{500}^0 > \sigma_{RT}^0, \quad \sigma_{500}^{0.2} > \sigma_{RT}^{0.2}$$

The strength depended on the effect of annealing on the particles.

Microstructure of green body and CNF

CNF generated bonding sites between CNF and particles.

- CNF sheet had dense fiber network structure.
- CNF network structure disappeared after annealing.
- Only the thick CNF bundle remained.
- Almost no difference in microstructure was observed between CNFs annealing at 250 °C and 500 °C.

Proposed strengthening mechanism by CNF addition

(Room temperature)

CNF strengthens SiC green body by increasing the number of bonding sites through hydrogen-bonding.

(250 °C)

CNF does not contribute to the matrix strength due to the loss of bound water.

(500 °C)

The partially-oxidized SiC particle surface is cleaned. Besides, non-polar groups (Si-C) are exposed^[2].

The residual pyrolyzed fiber bundle increases the number of bonding sites through van der Waals force.

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[1] T. Kanno et al., *Int J Adv Manuf Technol*, 125, pp.2055-2064 (2023).

[2] H. Kamiya et al., *Powder Technol*, 127, pp.239-245 (2002).